

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Near-Infrared Responsive Targeted Drug Delivery System That Offer Chemo-Photothermal Therapy Against Bacterial Infection

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1. Additional Experimental Section

Materials and instruments. Hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, 99%), L-ascorbic acid (AA, 98%), silver nitrate (AgNO_3 , 99%), hydrogen tetrachloroauric (III) acid trihydrate ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.9%), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 , 98%), tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS, 98%), 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES, 97%), 3-(aminopropyl)trimethoxysilane (APTMS) (97%), *N*-hydroxysulfosuccinimide sodium salt (sulfo-NHS), rhodamine B isothiocyanate isomer (RITC), 4',6'-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI, 98%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA). Sodium hydroxide (NaOH , 98.5%) was purchased from Lab Chem (Pennsylvania, USA). Ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3 , 99%) was purchased from ACROS Organics. 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC, 98%) was purchased from Alfa Aesar (Massachusetts, USA) and *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS, 99%), was purchased from TCI America (Portland, USA). Water was used from a Milli-Q water ultrapure water purification system (Millipore). Absolute ethanol (200 proof), sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS), chloroform (CHCl_3), HPLC grade acetonitrile (ACN), water with 1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, 1% v/v) HPLC grade were purchased from Fisher Scientific Inc., (Massachusetts, USA). 1,2-dipalmitoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC), cholesterol and 1,2-distearoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine-*N*-[amino(polyethylene glycol)-2000] (DSPE-PEG 2000 amine) and mini extruder kit were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids Inc., (Alabama, USA). *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl) piperazine-*N'*-(2-ethanesulfonic acid) (HEPES solution), MES buffer, 2',7'-Dichlorofluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA) reactive oxygen species kit (ROS) assay kit and cell counting kit WST-8 were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA). *Msmeg* strain mc² 155, (ATCC® 700084) was purchased from American Type Culture Collection (Vancouver, USA). Mycobacteria media Difco™ Middlebrook 7H9 broth, Difco™ Middlebrook 7H10 agar, BBL™ Middlebrook ADC enrichment and BBL™ Middlebrook OADC enrichment were purchased from Becton Dickinson (New Jersey, USA). A549 (ATCC® CCL-1851) lung cancer cells were also purchased from ATCC. Synthesized NZX peptide was purchased from ProteoGenix (Schiltigheim, France). MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) cell proliferation kit, live/dead® BacLight™ bacterial viability kit, Hoechst dye, 4',6'-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) and calcein AM were purchased from ThermoFisher Scientific (Massachusetts, USA). Ham's F-12K nutrient mixture with L-glutamine (F-12K, 1X), fetal bovine serum (FBS, 10%), trypsin EDTA (2.21 mM) and Penicillin Streptomycin (Pen-Strep, 1X) were purchased from Corning (New York, USA). The particle size was determined by using a Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) Malvern Zetasizer, Malvern Panalytical Inc., (Massachusetts, USA). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were obtained on a FEI Tecnai Osiris operating at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Nitrogen adsorption-desorption was performed using a surface area and porosity analyzer (Autosorb iQ-C-MP/XR,

USA). Absorbance spectra of particles and optical density measurements were performed with a Spectramax M2 Molecular Devices Ltd., plate reader (Silicon Valley, USA). Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopic analysis was done using Nicolet is50 ATR FTIR ThermoFisher Scientific (New Jersey, USA). Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed on a Discovery Q500, TGA from TA Instruments (Massachusetts, USA). High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) analysis were performed using a Hitachi Primaide Separation module and a 1430 diode array detector equipped with a reverse phase SunFire C18 column. The 808 nm laser diodes (G pin code) of 200 mW and 500 mW power intensities, laser diode controller (LDC210C), laser diode temperature controller (TED200C), laser diode mount (LDM56), digital thermometer, and 25 mm objective lens (LA1560) were all purchased from Thor Labs Inc., (New Jersey, USA). The fluorescence microscopy images were taken from CKX53 inverted fluorescence microscope, Olympus (USA). Mammalian cells were quantified using automatic cell counter (Corning, USA). All aseptic bacteria techniques and sterile mammalian cell culture were conducted in separate 1300 Series A2 bio safety cabinet (ThermoFisher Scientific). Shaking incubator (Corning, USA) and CO₂ incubator (ThermoFisher Scientific) were used for bacteria and mammalian cell culture incubation. Sterile disposables, sterilized glassware and medium were used for all experiments. Unless specifically mentioned, all liquid media were sterilized using a bench top BioClave liquid sterilizer (Ward's Science, New York, USA).

Setup for Laser Irradiation Studies with NIR Laser Diode. The thermo-optical setup used for this purpose is shown in Figure S1. The setup was used with two separate NIR diode lasers with 500 and 200 mW laser intensities (L808P500MM and L808P200) (Thor Labs, USA). The laser diode was fixed in a temperature-controlled mount (LDM56) (Thor Labs, USA), which is connected to the laser diode controller (LDC210C, Thor Labs, USA). Laser diode controller was used to control the intensity of the laser output power. The laser diode temperature controller (TED200C, Thor Labs, USA) helped maintain a stable output power, wavelength and prevent heating that can damage the laser diodes. The laser beam was focused to a spot size of ~ 2 mm diameter, with a 25 mm focal length objective lens to the middle of a single well in a 96 well plate. A thermocouple monitor was used to monitor the temperature of the solution upon exposure to the laser. *Msmeg* was treated with different concentrations of GNR@MSNP@BDQ and final nano assembly GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX and irradiated for 15 min with 200 mW and 500 mW laser. Control experiments were carried out without *Msmeg*. For each case, the photothermal-antibacterial efficacy of nano-assembly was studied. Power intensity of 500 mW was used for the entire study as 200 mW was insufficient to induce required hyperthermia effects.

Figure S1. Schematic illustration of the laser set up used for photothermal study.

Figure S2. Calibration curve of bedaquiline (BDQ) by HPLC.

Table S1. List of TSPR and LSPR peaks for various nano-assemblies measured by UV-Vis spectroscopy.

Nano-assemblies	TSPR peak (nm)	LSPR peak (nm)
GNR	514	790
GNR@MSNP	514	805
GNR@MSNP@BDQ	514	805
GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX	514	805

Figure S3. Labelled FT-IR spectrum for various nano-assemblies

Table S2. Characteristics peaks of various nano-assemblies in FT-IR spectra

Numbering	Characteristics peak (cm ⁻¹)	Functional groups	Nanomaterials
1	2847	Symmetric -CH ₂	GNR
2	2870	Asymmetric -CH ₂	
3	1473	-CH ₂ scissoring	
4	960	C-O stretching	
5	1064	Si-O-Si	GNR@MSNP
6	2922 ,2914	C- H stretching	GNR@MSNP@BDQ
7	1662	N-H stretching	
8	1407	C-C stretching	
9	1230	C-N stretching	GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX
10	2848	Symmetric -CH ₂	
11	2918	Asymmetric -CH ₂	
12	1650	Amide I	
13	1540	Amide II	
14	1241	C-O stretching	

**GNR@MSNP at 37 °C
in media**

Day 1

Day 5

**GNR@MSNP@TSL at 37 °C
in media**

Day 1

Day 5

Figure S4. Photographs of stability studies for GNR@MSNP and GNR@MSNP@TSL 37 °C in mammalian cell culture media.

Table 3. Quantification of nanomaterials by TGA.

Materials	Loading (%)
GNR@MSNP	NA
GNR@MSNP@BDQ	16 ± 0.5 (of BDQ)
GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL	10 ± 1.6 (of TSL)
GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX	12 ± 1.5 (of NZX)

Laser triggered TSL melting: To support the laser triggered photothermal (PT) activity-based melting of TSL, a fluorescent dye (green, fluorescent calcein) release assay was designed to demonstrate the PT triggered melting of TSL. TSL-calcein were prepared by encapsulating calcein in TSL by thin film method followed by extrusion.¹ Similarly, GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein were prepared. The release of calcein was measured in proportion to the fluorescence intensity of the solution. TSL-calcein and GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein was exposed to NIR laser for 15 min, and the fluorescence intensity quantified at 5 min intervals and the temperature change was recorded.

The percentage of calcein released from GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein with laser trigger was calculated using the following Equation 1. Before laser irradiation blank fluorescence (I_{pre}) was measured at an excitation wavelength 490 nm, emission wavelength 515 nm. Fluorescence intensity (I_{post}) was measured after laser irradiation (808 nm, 15 min). The fluorescence intensity (I_{100}), due to a 100% release of calcein from TSL-calcein was recorded by solubilizing TSL in detergent Triton-X100.

Equation 1.

$$\% \text{ Calcein release} = \frac{I_{post} - I_{pre}}{I_{100\%} - I_{pre}} \times 100\% \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

The melting of TSL was evaluated by calcein dye leakage assay as shown in Figure S5. The fluorescent intensity from GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein increased continuously after laser irradiation compared with TSL-calcein (Figure S5a). The PT effect of GNRs caused a rise in temperature upto 60 ± 3 °C for 15 min. which helps permeate the TSL and increase release of calcein (Figure S5a and Figure S5b). Figure S5a shows the increase in calcein release upon increase in laser irradiation time and Figure S5b displays calcein intensity with the change in temperature. When the temperature reaches and surpasses the melting point (48 ± 3 °C) of TSL, the maximum release of calcein occur (Figure S5c). It is noteworthy that fluorescence intensity increased rapidly from temperature range of 40 – 55

°C, where the range includes the melting point of TSL. The observed melting point of TSL was quantified to be 48 ± 3 °C. The percentage release of calcein was quantified as can be seen in Figure S5c. Calcein release from TSL-calcein was low ($2.5 \pm 1.1\%$) when compared to GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein ($70.11 \pm 1.3\%$) after 15 min of laser irradiation. From this release profile (Figure S5c) we can see that 35% of calcein from 70% total release was between the temperature range of 40 – 55 °C. Since, the measured melting point of TSL was 48 ± 3 °C, the higher calcein release can be positively correlated to the melting of the TSL. In addition, the continuous temperature increase in the system can be seen only in the presence of GNRs in GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein (Figure S5b) which confirms PT effect of GNRs. From these observations it is apparent that calcein release increased in the range of the melting point of TSL which confirms the correlation of PT activity of GNRs with the subsequent melting of TSL.

Figure S5. Change in calcein release from TSL-calcein and GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein. (a) Change in fluorescent intensity with laser irradiation times for TSL-calcein and GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein. (b) Change in fluorescence intensity with temperature in TSL-calcein and GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein. (c) Percentage release of calcein from TSL-calcein and GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL-calcein after irradiating with laser for 15min.

Morphological changes of *Msmeg* observed through TEM: The morphological changes of *Msmeg* after treatment with various nano-assemblies were observed through TEM. *Msmeg* (10^8 CFU/mL) was treated with GNR@MSNP@BDQ and GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX and exposed to NIR laser for 15 min, followed by incubation (37 °C, 4 h). Bacteria was pelleted and washed by centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 10 min and fixed with 2.5% glutaraldehyde for 4 h at 4 °C. After washing 3x with HEPES, the bacteria was dehydrated in a graded series of ethanol (30%–100% v/v) for 30 min and imaged through TEM operating at 200 kV.

Figure S6a-a shows that laser irradiated GNR@MSNP@BDQ has minimal damage to cell membrane of bacteria. In contrast, when laser irradiated GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX is treated with *Msmeg*, increased surface aggregation of GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX is seen on *Msmeg*. The surface aggregation compromises the outer cell membrane integrity and eventually complete degradation of *Msmeg* (Figure S6a-b, red arrows indicate degraded cells). The loss of outer membrane integrity is due to the physical aberrations caused by nano-assemblies pressing hard against the surface. NZX mediated adhesion is the probable cause for the high interaction between *Msmeg* and the GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX. These TEM studies show possible NZX peptide mediated adhesion of GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX and high antibacterial activity upon NIR laser exposure (Figure S6a-b). The schematic illustration in Figure S6b shows NZX mediated adhesion of GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX on *Msmeg* surface (pink block), PT activity and disintegration of TSL upon NIR irradiation (red block) and BDQ release and lysis of *Msmeg* (grey block).

Figure S6. (a) Morphological changes observed under TEM, of *Msmeg* after treatment with various nano-assemblies upon laser exposure. The scale bars are 1 μm . (b) Schematic illustrated the mechanism of action of final nano-assembly GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX upon interacting with *Msmeg*.

Cell cytotoxicity live-dead assay conducted on host A549 cells. Live -dead assay was conducted on lung cells treated with GNR@MSNP, GNR@MSNP@BDQ and GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX after laser irradiation. A549 cells were seeded onto 24 well plate at a density of 1×10^3 cells/well (1 mL per well). After reaching 90% confluence, cells were treated with (0.5, mg/mL) of GNR@MSNP@BDQ and final nano-assembly GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX for 18 h at 37 °C. Treated cells were exposed to NIR laser 808 nm, 500 mW for 15 min. A549 cells treated with nano-assemblies were stained with SYTO 9 and propidium iodide (PI) for 30 min at 37°C. Finally, the live and dead cells were examined under an inverted fluorescence microscope.

The live-dead assay consists of two fluorescent dyes (propidium iodide and SYTO 9) that differentially label live (green) and dead (red) cells.² Due to the compromised plasma membrane of the dead cell, propidium iodide (PI) intake increases, which subsequently binds to the nucleic acids, resulting in red fluorescence. SYTO 9 dye labels intact plasma membrane, hence viable cells appear in green fluorescence.

As shown in Figure S7 lung cells incubated with GNR@MSNP@BDQ and GNR@MSNP@BDQ@TSL@NZX even after laser irradiation appears to be live (green fluorescent). It is apparent by live-dead assay, PTT applied by laser irradiation has minimal cytotoxic effects on the lung cells.

Figure S7. Fluorescence microscopy images of the live/dead assay. Live/dead assay performed on A549 cells treated with different nano-assemblies for 18 h with laser exposure. Scale bar: 50 μm .

References

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- (2) Gordon, J. L.; Brown, M.; Reynolds, M. *Diseases* **2018**, *6*.